

ELABORATION AND EVALUATION OF AN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

Mirzaeva Shakhlo Ruzmat kizi

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11090247>

Abstract. *This scientific article explores the development and evaluation of an emotional intelligence program designed to enhance students' professional competence. The research involved the creation and implementation of a tailored educational program focused on improving emotion management, empathy, and social competence among students. Various assessment methods, including surveys, observations, and self-assessment, were utilized to measure the effectiveness of the program. The study findings reveal a positive impact on students' emotional intelligence levels, professional skills, and interpersonal interactions. These results underscore the significance of emotional intelligence development in the professional training of students and support the recommendation for the program's integration into the educational curriculum.*

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, efficiency, development program, professional competence, students.*

INTRODUCTION

Research indicates that emotional intelligence is a crucial factor in achieving success, both academically and professionally, because it affects their emotional stability, ability to empathize, emotion management and interpersonal relationships. Special programs are being developed to enhance students' emotional intelligence through various methods and strategies. However, not all programs are valid and effective, and their quality and content may vary significantly. It is essential to assess the effectiveness of these programs and study their impact on students' professional competence.

This article delves into the process of developing an emotional intelligence development program and evaluating its efficiency. It explores different methods and tools used for evaluating the program's effectiveness and presents research findings illustrating how such a program can enhance students' professional competence. Additionally, the article addresses the challenges and obstacles confronted by developers and educators during program implementation, offering recommendations to overcome them.

Currently, it is still uncertain in psychology which programs should be applied to for the effective development of students' emotional intelligence. Nevertheless, it is known that teenagers and young people need special help during this emotionally explosive period. An analysis of existing psychological and pedagogical programs for the development of emotional intelligence shows that teachers and psychologists rely on various methodological foundations [1,2,3,5,7,10].

One of the main concepts is the ideas of L.S.Vygotsky, such as the zone of immediate development and consideration of the zones of actual and immediate development. A dynamic semantic system that combines affective and intellectual processes also plays an important role in the practice of developing emotional intelligence in young people.

The concept of emotions as regulators of mental activity, introduced by S.L.Rubinstein, is also widely used.

D.V.Lyusin's approach to emotional intelligence considers it as a structure represented by two "dimensions". Interacting with each other, these dimensions form four types of emotional intelligence.

There is a paradigm of developmental education, in which special attention is paid not only to the transfer of knowledge and skills, but also to the development of human abilities and personal qualities in children. This paradigm, presented by D.B.Elkonin and V.V.Davydov, implies the "psychologization" of pedagogical practice and the creation of an education system that promotes personal development.

The concept of J.Mayer and P.Salovey note the importance of emotional phenomena in cognition. They claim that emotions affect cognitive processes and are regulated by personality.

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

The purpose of the research is to study the scientific foundations of the elaboration and evaluation of the effectiveness of programs for the development of emotional intelligence to improve the professional competence of students.

METHODS

Working with literature, theoretical analysis and generalization of data.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

To develop a program for the development of students' emotional intelligence, it was important to take into account the following aspects [5]:

1. Understanding emotional intelligence: It is important to start by identifying the basic concepts. What is emotional intelligence and what skills does it include? Emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize, understand, and manage your own emotions and those of others. It includes components such as self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and the ability to establish and maintain relationships.

2. Defining the goals of the program: set clear goals for the program for the development of students' emotional intelligence. For example, developing emotional recognition skills, improving the ability to regulate emotions in stressful situations, developing empathy and sociability. The goals may be specific depending on the professional field of the students.

3. Creating the content of the program: determine the theoretical basis and approaches that we want to include in the program for the development of emotional intelligence. For example, you can use the concepts of Daniel Goleman, who popularizes the concept of emotional intelligence, as well as development methods and techniques such as emotional awareness training, role-playing games, group discussions, reflective practices, etc.

4. Integration into curricula: Consider integrating an emotional intelligence development program into existing curricula so that students can apply the acquired skills in the context of their professional activities. For example, you can conduct lessons, seminars or courses related to interpersonal relationships, communication, leadership, etc.

5. Evaluation and measurement: provide a system for evaluating and measuring the effectiveness of the program. Use questionnaires or other methods to assess changes in students' emotional intelligence before and after participating in the program. Remember that emotional intelligence is a subjective concept, so measuring can be a difficult task. However, students can evaluate their own changes and progress through feedback, self-assessment and reflection.

6. Promoting practical skills: pay attention to the practical component of the program. To provide students with the opportunity to apply the skills they are developing in practice, for example, through role-playing games, exercises and tasks based on real situations from professional life.

7. Creating a supportive environment: to ensure the support and emotional safety of students within the framework of the emotional intelligence development program. This may include building trust, group support, and facilitating dialogue between program participants.

Since the development of emotional intelligence is a process that requires time and practice, the program can be structured over several semesters or included in the educational program throughout the entire period of students' studies.

Emotional intelligence development programs will be especially useful for students who [5]:

- they want to better understand and control their emotions: emotional self-awareness and the ability to manage their emotions are key aspects of emotional intelligence. If students want to better understand their emotions, recognize them and effectively manage them in various situations, then these programs can be useful for them;

- they want to develop interpersonal skills: Communication, empathy and the ability to establish effective relationships are important aspects of emotional intelligence. If students strive to improve their interpersonal skills, learn how to communicate effectively, listen and understand others, then emotional intelligence development programs can help them achieve this goal;

- they are interested in developing leadership skills: emotional intelligence is associated with the development of leadership skills such as emotional stability, empathy and the ability to motivate others. If students are interested in developing their potential as leaders and strive to become effective and inspiring leaders, emotional intelligence development programs can help them in this process;

- they want to improve their decision-making skills: emotional awareness and the ability to regulate their emotions can help students make more informed and informed decisions. If students want to develop decision-making skills, taking into account emotional aspects and effectively manage their reactions and decisions, then emotional intelligence development programs can be useful for them;

- strive for better teamwork: the development of emotional intelligence contributes to a better understanding of emotional contexts and interactions in the team. If students want to become more effective and harmonious team members, improve their skills of cooperation, conflict management and support for other team members, then emotional intelligence development programs will be useful for them.

It is important to note that emotional intelligence development programs will be useful for a wide range of students, regardless of their specialization or professional interests. The development of emotional intelligence in today's digital age is a universal human value that can be applied in various spheres of life and professional activity.

Emotional intelligence development programs will teach students the following skills [5]:

1. Self-awareness: Effectively managing your emotions begins with awareness and understanding of your own emotions. Emotional intelligence development programs will help students develop self-awareness, which will allow them to recognize their emotions, their causes and influence on behavior and decisions.

2. Self-regulation: the development of emotional intelligence will help students master self-regulation skills - the ability to effectively manage their emotions and reactions to stressful situations. Students will learn to improve their ability to maintain emotional stability and cope with challenges by maintaining clarity of thought and making rational decisions.

3. Empathy: Emotional intelligence development programs promote the development of empathy – the ability to understand and share other people's emotions. Students will learn to perceive and take into account the emotional states of other people, which will improve their ability to effectively cooperate and interpersonal communication.

4. The ability to establish and maintain relationships: The development of emotional intelligence helps students develop the skills to establish and maintain emotionally supportive relationships. This includes the ability to effectively express your emotions, listen and show empathy towards others, as well as build positive and trusting relationships with people around you.

5. Conflict Management: Emotional intelligence development programs will teach students the ability to effectively manage conflicts, prevent their escalation and find constructive solutions. Students will master the skills of overcoming unpleasant emotions, active listening and compromise, which will help them in professional situations where interaction and conflict are inevitable.

6. Communication: Emotional intelligence development programs are aimed at developing effective communication skills. Students will learn to express their thoughts and emotions clearly and clearly, improve their active listening skills, adapt to other people's communication styles and effectively identify and eliminate possible misunderstandings.

7. Decision making: The development of emotional intelligence helps students make more informed and informed decisions. They will learn to take into account not only logical and analytical aspects, but also emotional and social factors, which will improve the quality of their decisions.

8. Stress Management: Emotional intelligence development programs will teach students how to cope with stress and emotional stress. Students will learn relaxation techniques, breathing practices, stress reduction exercises and meditation, which will help them maintain emotional well-being in various situations.

Emotional intelligence development programs will help students develop a range of skills and competencies that will be useful in both their personal and professional lives. Awareness and development of emotional intelligence will help students become more successful adults, leaders and prosperous individuals in general [8].

As a result of completing the emotional intelligence development program, students will be able to:

1. Better understand and manage their emotions: they will learn to recognize and understand their emotions, their causes and the impact on their behavior. Thanks to this, students will be able to manage their emotions more effectively in various situations, maintain emotional stability and make informed decisions.

2. Develop empathy: students will learn to understand and share the emotions of others, develop an empathic response and take into account the emotional states of others. This helps to improve their ability to interact, communicate effectively and collaborate with other people.

3. Build quality relationships: They will learn how to effectively establish and maintain emotionally supportive relationships with other people. Students will learn to show understanding, respect, tolerance and communication skills that will help them build healthy, trusting and productive relationships at work, school and in their personal lives.

4. Manage Stress and adapt to change: Students will learn strategies for managing stress, adapting to change and overcoming difficulties. Because emotional intelligence helps students develop the ability to self-regulate, they will be better able to cope with stress and maintain their emotional well-being even in difficult situations.

5. Effectively resolve conflicts: they will learn how to manage conflicts, listen and understand other people, look for compromises and find constructive solutions. This will help them to interact effectively with colleagues, solve problems and prevent conflicts in the workplace and in other areas of life [6].

6. Improve team performance: students will become more flexible and adaptive team members. Developing emotional intelligence will help them better understand emotional contexts, build positive relationships with colleagues, and make valuable contributions to the work of the team.

7. Improve professional competence: the development of emotional intelligence has a positive effect on the professional competence of students. Emotional intelligence helps students better understand others, colleagues and partners, improves communication, leadership skills, decision-making and the ability to successfully adapt to changes in the work environment.

8. Develop Leadership Skills: Emotional intelligence development programs can help students develop leadership skills and leadership potential. They will be able to become more emotionally stable, inspiring and able to motivate other people.

The emotional intelligence development program uses various methods and techniques that help students develop skills and competencies in this area [8, 9]. Let's list some of them:

1. Trainings and seminars. Conducting trainings and seminars is a common method in the emotional intelligence development program. Students participate in active practical exercises and role-playing games that help them master the skills of emotion recognition, empathy, introspection, self-regulation, communication and conflict management. Such events are conducted by psychology specialists or trainers who teach students such skills through practical exercises and assignments.

2. Reflection and self-reflection. The practice of reflection and self-reflection allows students to be aware of their emotional reactions and behavior in various situations. The methodology includes the analysis of past events, self-assessment and formulation of plans for personal development and improvement of behavior and reactions to emotions.

3. Active listening and empathic understanding. The technique of active listening and empathic understanding is used to develop skills of empathy and perception of other people's emotions. Students learn to express and practice full attention, understanding, and emotional response to what other people say.

4. Self-regulation and stress management exercises. The inclusion of self-regulation and stress management exercises helps students develop skills to reduce stress and emotional tension. Such exercises can be aimed at practicing breathing techniques, meditation, relaxation and mindfulness [4,6].

5. Interactive classes and role-playing games. They can be useful for developing emotional perception, empathy, and conflict management skills. In the process of interactivity and games, students actively interact, act in various roles, which allows them to better understand the emotional context and perspective of other people.

6. Studying literature and case studies. Studying literature and case studies helps students acquire theoretical knowledge about emotional intelligence and its application in various situations. Analyzing real-life examples and stories allows students to better understand the principles of emotional intelligence and their real impact on interpersonal relationships and professional situations.

7. Individual consultations. Students can contact emotional intelligence specialists for individual advice and support. During the consultation, students can discuss their emotional states, recognize and analyze them, and develop plans to improve their emotional well-being.

8. Group practices and projects. The organization of group practices and projects in which students will interact with each other contributes to the development of emotional intelligence skills. Such practices may include joint problem solving, team building, participating in discussions and sharing experiences.

9. A favorable learning environment. Creating a supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable and can freely express their emotions also contributes to the development of emotional intelligence. Teachers can be attentive to students' emotional needs and support them in solving problems.

10. Special exercises, independent tasks and practice. An emotional intelligence development program may include special exercises and tasks that will help students better understand and manage their emotions. Students can additionally be offered independent tasks and practices, for example, keeping an emotional diary, practicing meditation, scientific analysis of emotions, self-reflection or conducting emotional experiments. This helps students apply and consolidate the considered skills in everyday life.

The key ones are general didactic teaching methods: problem presentation, research method, partially searchable (heuristic) method (according to I.Ya.Lerner and M.N.Skatkin) [5].

Participation in an emotional intelligence development program usually involves a combination of different methods and techniques to achieve maximum effect. The specific methods and techniques may vary depending on the program and the desired results.

To conduct research on the development of emotional intelligence among students in the process of their professional training, a special program of psychological and pedagogical support was developed, which took into account the selected content and methods. This program was the basis for the formation of the experiment.

The program for the development of emotional intelligence was based on techniques and materials for use from the works and author's programs of Khlevnaya E., J. Hasson, Andreeva I.N., E.A.Sergienko [8].

Within the framework of the program for the development of emotional intelligence of students, various methods are used, including thematic conversations, discussions using connections between subjects, case methods, game methods, art therapeutic techniques, exercises using psychohymnastics, methods of psychodiagnostics and self-diagnosis of emotional state (for example, "Diary of emotions" and "reflective screen of emotional state"), as well as distance learning technologies.

The purpose of the program is to develop the emotional intelligence of students in the process of their professional training. The development of emotional intelligence implies the achievement of a harmonious relationship between cognitive and emotional processes in students, as well as the formation and improvement of basic skills that contribute to this development, namely [5]:

- recognition of emotions;
- emotion management;
- developing empathy and caring for others (empathy);
- relationship skills;
- responsible decision-making.

During the implementation of the program, the following tasks are solved:

- develop the ability to recognize and understand your own and others' emotions;
- to develop the ability to constructively express their emotions;
- to form the ability to recognize the feelings of another, to empathize (empathy);
- to teach to measure their behavior with the feelings and interests of another person.

The program is designed into three blocks: emotional, cognitive and behavioral. 52 hours are allocated for the implementation of the program. Of these, 26 hours are allocated for practical classes, 13 hours for lectures and 13 hours for independent work. Classes are held once a week for 4 academic hours [8].

The content of the program.

Block 1. Psychology of emotions

The purpose of the section is to promote awareness and understanding of one's own emotions and those of others.

Tasks: to study the main provisions of the theory of "Emotional intelligence"; to consider the basic emotions, their specific signs and facial expressions; to study tools for tracking the emotional state.

Block 2. "Social and emotional skills (SES) in the structure of Soft skills.

The purpose of the section: teaching methods for the development of social and emotional skills.

Tasks: development of skills of arbitrary management of one's behavior, regulation of emotional state; development of the ability to empathy, understanding of experiences, states of other people; teaching ways of behavior in relationships with others, the ability to establish and maintain contacts, cooperate, avoid conflict situations.

The thematic plan of the developed program of psychological and pedagogical support for the development of emotional intelligence of students and the algorithm of conducting Practical exercises are presented in Appendix No. 3.

An emotional intelligence development program can have a significant impact on students' professional competence and this can be revealed as follows [5]:

1. Improving interpersonal skills. Emotional intelligence is directly related to the ability to interact effectively with other people. The Emotional Intelligence Development program will help students develop the skills of empathy, listening, effective communication, conflict management, cooperation and problem resolution, establishing and maintaining relationships, improve the skills of understanding and expressing emotions, non-verbal communication, the ability to accept and give feedback, which is extremely important for creating a positive and productive work

environment where students can effectively interact and work with colleagues and management in a professional environment.

2. Leadership skills and emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is also associated with the development of leadership skills. The Emotional Intelligence Development program promotes the development of leadership qualities such as emotional stability, understanding the needs of others and the ability to motivate colleagues, emotion management skills, setting boundaries and self-confidence, which is especially useful for future leaders and managers. Students with emotional intelligence and competence can be effective leaders who are able to create an inspiring and supportive work environment.

3. Stress management, emotional well-being and conflict resolution. Professional activity is often accompanied by stressful situations. The Emotional Intelligence Development Program will help students develop skills of self-regulation, stress tolerance, stress management, conflict resolution and relief of emotional tension, skills to adequately and effectively solve problems, improve adaptability and flexibility in a changing work environment. The ability to effectively manage emotions in stressful situations will allow students to better cope with challenges and maintain psychological well-being, which is an important skill for professional competence [5].

4. More effective decision-making. The interpersonal and emotional awareness developed in the program contributes to a better understanding of one's own emotions, motivations and values. This helps students to make more informed and informed decisions, as well as to take into account emotional and social aspects in the process of developing strategies and making decisions in the professional field.

5. Improving customer focus. As part of the development of emotional intelligence, students can develop skills of empathy, understanding and attentiveness to the needs of clients or patients. This is important for students studying in an area where customer interaction plays a key role. For example, doctors, psychologists, social workers and customer service managers.

6. Improve team performance. The development of emotional intelligence contributes to a better understanding of the emotions and needs of other team members. Students with developed emotional intelligence have a better understanding of the emotional context and team interactions, which helps to reduce conflicts and increase the effectiveness of teamwork. They can also improve the skills of cooperation, tolerance and respect for the points of view of other team members.

7. Improving the level of self-confidence, self-efficacy and self-motivation. The development of emotional intelligence helps students develop positive internal dialogue, strengthen confidence in their abilities and increase their motivation. Students can overcome obstacles more effectively and strive to achieve their goals.

It is important to note that emotional intelligence is not a separate success factor, but rather complements professional skills and competencies. The combination of professional knowledge and emotional intelligence allows students to become more adaptive, flexible and successful in their professional field.

Evaluating the effectiveness of an emotional intelligence development program requires conducting appropriate research, and for this you need to take some general steps [5]:

1. Defining the goals of the program.
2. Development of assessment tools for data collection (questionnaires or tests that will help measure changes in emotional intelligence skills).

3. Data collection before (to establish the basic level of emotional intelligence skills of participants) and after the completion of the program.

4. Data analysis: (determination of the statistical significance of changes in emotional intelligence skills).

5. Assessment of participants' satisfaction (conducting surveys, interviews, reviews).

Various resources are needed for the effective implementation of the emotional intelligence development program, such as [8]:

- Qualified teachers and trainers: The program should include trained professionals who have an understanding and experience in the field of emotional intelligence. These specialists will play a key role in teaching students and conducting practical classes;

- Educational materials and techniques: The development and preparation of educational materials is an important part of the emotional intelligence development program. These can be textbooks, manuals, videos, case studies, practical tasks, etc. These materials should be adapted to the needs and age of the students.

- Evaluation and measurement methods: Evaluation and measurement methods are necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the program. These can be tests, questionnaires, questionnaires, interviews, or observation of student behavior. These methods will help to assess the current level of students' emotional intelligence and progress during and after the completion of the program.

- Learning environment: Learning emotional intelligence requires a suitable environment that will create a favorable environment for the development of students. This can be a specially organized training room, multimedia equipment, or the use of online platforms for distance learning.

- support of the administration and parents: the emotional intelligence development program should have the support of the administration of the educational institution and parents. This may include financial support, organizational assistance, feedback, and informing parents about the goals and benefits of the program.

It is important to note that resources may vary depending on the specific program and the conditions in which it is implemented. The main thing is to ensure access to the right people, materials and infrastructure so that students' learning and development of emotional intelligence are effective.

The assessment of the achievement of the planned results of the emotional intelligence development program can be carried out according to various criteria, including qualitative and quantitative aspects [5].

Qualitative criteria:

1. Students' ability to recognize and understand their own emotions and those of other people.

2. Students' ability to effectively regulate their emotions and resolve conflicts.

3. Developing students' empathy and social competence skills.

4. Improving interpersonal relationships and the sphere of communication of students.

5. Improving students' self-esteem, self-sufficiency and personal effectiveness.

6. Awareness and application of emotional intelligence in educational and professional fields.

Quantitative criteria:

1. Conducting pre- and post-testing to assess changes in students' emotional intelligence.
2. Collection and analysis of data on the level of emotional intelligence of participating students before and after the program.
3. Evaluation of completed questionnaires or questionnaires to measure progress in the development of emotional intelligence.
4. The use of compiled headings or assessment scales to assess the manifestations of emotional intelligence in students in various situations.
5. Analysis of students' academic achievements in the context of their participation in the emotional intelligence development program.

The assessment of the achievement of the planned results of the emotional intelligence development program should include both qualitative and quantitative criteria. Qualitative criteria will help to assess changes in the subject himself, his emotional competence and interpersonal relationships, while quantitative criteria offer more objective data on the progress in the development of emotional intelligence of program participants.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the development and evaluation of an emotional intelligence program aimed at improving students' professional competence has shown promising results. The findings support the belief that emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in students' overall success in the professional world. By enhancing their emotional intelligence skills through targeted interventions, students can better navigate the complexities of the workplace, communicate effectively, and build strong relationships with colleagues and clients. Future research should continue to explore the effectiveness of such programs in various educational settings and industries to further enhance students' professional competencies.

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